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The Challenge of Achieving Innovative Organisations in the Indian Context

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Abstract

Taking a philosophical position like the quote above, in this paper the authors have attempted a perceptive critique in the Indian context to focus on management initiatives towards promoting learning and innovation in organisations based on his two decades of research mainly in Western India, and in the process, dealing with quality of mindsets. In the process the author has looked at innovation and learning as the solution to various problems organizations face and their justification. Once having established the veracity of this claim, innovation and learning as the panacea for a majority of organizational ills, the author has concentrated on the line of thought and policies firms have to internalise to implement these credos. Innovation and creativity, he argues, like Sheridan (1998) must be imbibed in the organizational culture and cannot be spasmodic activities undertaken by individuals in the management. For this to happen, top management must move out of the feudal-mercantilist-trader mindset and adopt the creative- innovative-entrepreneurial mindset. Insecure and inexperienced top management usually find it difficult to make this transition. The inevitable result is that while the organisations become poor the owners individually get rich, innovation flies out of the window just as sycophancy enters the door. And this is a situation no civil society desirous of achieving developmental growth can or should tolerate.

Keywords: Organisational culture, Innovation, Creativity, Strategic initiatives, Indian context Equilibrium, Values

Introduction

George Orwell in *The Paradox of Causation* wrote thus: “An effect can become a cause, reinforcing the original cause and producing the same effect in an intensified form, and so on indefinitely.” Innovation and learning are not new concepts. They have existed from the time mankind invented the wheel and even before that when primitive mankind discovered fire earlier. But in the age of the intellect where organisations are forced by the objective market reality to thrive on the cutting edge of competition, quality deliverables and excellence became business imperatives. It was argued by scholars and by that the greatest hindrance to organisational progress is the mediocrat – bureaucrat who tries to guard his turf since he is inherently insecure. [Jayashree (1999) Sadri and Jayashree (2002)]. This could be because of an abject paucity of a required competence or the fact that he has risen up the ranks through boot licking. Hence they had argued that as long as this mediocratic bureaucracy is not marginalised progress and quality deliverables will be difficult to attain. Later the *strategic triad*, was posited wherein it was argued that “business ethics and corporate governance combine to provide the basis for organisational excellence.” [Jayashree’s (1996) (2012)]. This theme was expanded and reiterated at length and the triad itself was expanded to include business sustainability. [Sadri and Jayashree (2011) and Jayashree’s (2012)]. Excellence was seen like a rainbow that the organisation could move towards but not attain since once the point of excellence was reached, the goal posts would be moved further away. Besides the mediocrat bureaucrat, the other main impediments to excellence were inadequate diagnosis before any strategic intervention was mooted and insufficient analysis once it was implemented. The authors went further and argued that “excellence cannot be an end in itself”. After all, we only have to look at Rolls Royce Corporation and their historic car project to see that excellence by itself is not enough. It was further argued that excellence must inevitably lead to business sustainability and quality deliverables were an integral condition for achieving sustainability. OD interventions could merely create the conditions within which quality deliverables could be produced and business sustainability could be achieved: both through a relentless pursuit of excellence.[Sadri Jayashree and Sharma (2013)]

Schema

This paper is based on investigations carried out between 2010 and 2013 in the Indian context. The purpose of this paper is to use perceptive critique and encourage a debate towards a guideline for organization to meet the challenges of a fluid, dynamic environment. Based on our assertion that adopting an orientation towards innovation is the only way to survive, we have tried to identify the values, and practices that must be adopted in order to achieve this goal. During the past two decades, Total Quality Management (TQM) programmes have been implemented in many organizations but only some 50% of these have been successful (in India). The authors have discovered that in most cases where TQM has failed top management has paid lip-service to the idea and not put their heart and mind into making it work. According to some there has been a paucity of systematic empirical research to prescribe the necessary interventions. This may well be true to a large extent, and through the medium of this paper, we seek to address this issue. [Mohanty and Lakhe (2003)].

In this paper the authors have, albeit cursorily, examined various theories of innovation, change and learning and how they relate to modern organization. They have looked at the organization holistically with a systemic view, rather than a piecemeal functional one. All the premises he has utilized in this research paper are based on this fundamental principle. Further they have evolved and isolated a number of factors, which he believes are of prime importance when organization need to look at innovation and change as credos. These factors help in embedding and inculcating a culture and a set of core values in the organization. They have also looked at what needs to be done with this set of factors and what practices and policies learning and innovation led companies the world over are adopting. Consequently the paper opines that, once an organizational culture is in place wherein the human element is given the requisite respect and attention, technology and operations will take be relatively easy to take care of. Although they have attempted to identify and isolate all factors that effect and are necessary to embed a culture of learning and innovation, we believe that it is an inherently self-defeating task. It is almost impossible to look at each and every factor and then evaluate its effect. Most of these factors are overlapping. We have therefore refrained from providing any solution as to how these factors, could be made suitable to the Indian environment and how systems and processes can be evolved and sustained.

Instead, we have written about a fostering and sustaining environment as well as honesty of purpose on the part of top management that inculcates learning and innovation, but have provided no recipe in this paper for doing so. [Jayashree (2012)], The authors believe that it is an organization and context-specific activity. Each and every organization will have to find its own solutions and then the most suitable ways to implement them. Here we have also looked at markets and the general business environment as well as the need to think in a *constructively illogical manner* or in an *upside down fashion* as some authors have variously advocated. [G B Shaw (1932), Charles Handy (1995), Stephen Somogyi (1998), Tara and Sharma, (2012), Sadri (2013)]

As the speed of change increases and as the complexities of life and of the workplace expand, the assumptions underlying models such as these, as well as traditional views of organizations and their leadership, will no longer tolerate violation. They rely too heavily on a belief in linearity and predictability. Hence they have to be discarded and innovative methods must replace them [Bass (1990)]. In the Indian case top management was often found to be more concerned with the *process* than with the *purpose* of the system with the result that progress was stymied.

Why should organizations today be concerned with fostering creativity and innovation? This moot point was raised by several authors before us. [Williams and Stephen (2010)]. Business research conducted by us on successful and failed companies in the SME Sector in India also identified five key reasons: (a) Superior long-term financial performance is associated with innovation. (b) Customers are increasingly demanding innovation, and companies due to *managerial myopia* fail to deliver. (c) Competitors are becoming better at copying past innovations, Japan's reverse engineering being a case in point. (d) New technologies enable innovation through research on business success and failure in technology-intensive industries illustrates a simple principle. [Joseph L. Bower and Clayton M. Christensen's (1995)]. If a company does not exploit innovative technology its competitors will, and they will take the market with them. (e) What used to work does not work anymore as objective social reality itself has changed. More of the same processes will result in more of the same disasters! [C J Nemeth (1997)]. There was one more reason identified by us and that was the abject inability of top management to give up the habit of becoming personally rich as their organisations became poor. The toothless governance mechanisms available to regulatory bodies and the political connections of the top management usually made such aggrandizement easy to practice.

We found that in the SME (small and medium enterprises) sector of India most unfortunately the words *innovation and creativity* rang a hollow bell unless top management became the change they wish to see. This did happen as in many small pharmaceutical companies and cold steel rolling mills where management behaved in the feudal-mercantilist-trader mode and primitive exploitation was the order of the day. Top management that was insecure spread this insecurity by poor planning and poorer executions, knee jerk reactions to crises and the resultant evolution of a work culture that was the very anti-thesis of trust-transparency and teamwork became the dominant contra development mechanism. Whoever did not agree with them is dubbed "anti-management" and as a philosopher would have said *as you know, the Inquisition is an admirable and wholly Christian invention to make the pope and the monks more powerful and turn a whole kingdom into hypocrites.* [Voltaire (1759)]. Replace the word Christian with industry, the pope with the CEO and the monks with corporate henchmen and one can see what failed businesses very often typify.

A. Case in Point

A Group of Institutes near Rajpura in Punjab was set up by a Pharmaceutical Company in 2009 and by 2012 top management was gung-ho about converting these institutions into a Private University. A Letter of Intent was also received but then things did not happen as envisaged. The feudal-mercantilist-trader mindset of the owners refused to be transformed. Autocratic and knee jerk reactions from the top became so prevalent that any positive suggestion which the top did not concur with was dubbed as being anti-management activity. By 2011 the Pharmaceutical Group had begun its downward spiral with several of its units being shut down. Other business ventures of the Group followed suit and with it the feudal-mercantilist-trader attitude of top management became even more pronounced. Admission to its various programs plummeted and neither the faculty nor the students were happy about the new culture of imposing fines at the drop of a handkerchief that emerged. Sycophants and the mediocrity that survived

by mouthing “ yes sir, yes sir, three bags full sir” were tolerated. The others were eyed with suspicion. Faculty attrition increased and despite good intentions and a good physical infrastructure the work climate was detrimental to progress.

Innovation comes out of self-confidence and creativity comes out of freedom to think. Both come from a mature, self confident and trust generating work culture. A vital attribute of the technological revolution is the increasing importance of innovation and the diffusion of this innovation into the marketplace. It had earlier been argued that we are in the age of mass customization, where we can have even highly complex products manufactured to our personal specifications in a short period of time. [Peters and Waterman (1982)] Speed now is of critical importance, while dramatic, radical innovations will frequently occur and be difficult to predict. Because of frequent radical innovations, there is increasing emphasis on designing new products and moving them to the marketplace rapidly. Consequently, change (currently) is technology driven and takes its toll on humankind. Change in human behaviour is evolutionary requiring an incrementation and an internalisation (settling in) period. Technological changes are on the other hand, are radical, non linear and non-Newtonian. Thus change today is dehumanising. We need to evolve to a platform wherein change harmonises co-existence of humankind and technology under the *new capitalism* as [Sadri and Jayashree (2011)]

Assuming that the student is a product and not a customer as is erroneously believed we could perhaps take a cue from the following "Best Practices" for successful product innovation projects that are now well established: (a) Linking market with technology so that conceptualisation, development, manufacture, launch and ongoing management are enabled. (b) People from all departments must be involved in all aspects of the innovation process from working with customers to considering manufacturing options. Product innovation is inherently multi-functional so we go into the realms of multi functional problem solving. (c) New product development projects must be evaluated over a period of time, often extending beyond the formal development phase itself so that they are relevant. (d) People must feel committed to innovation since it requires enormous investment in time, psychic energy, and attention. [Don Abraham (1998)]

If one were to take the view that there is an urgent need for organisations to look at how to: (a) start thinking outside the 'strategic planning' box and begin to examine how they actually learn, (b) complement vertical information flows with horizontal personal relationships, (c) build a trust-based culture by spreading a message of genuine openness, and (d) share all the information that has traditionally been a source of power. All these four activities need structured processes and a single minded devotion to quality, excellence and sustainability on the part of interventions. Invariably this needs to be explained further through a model so that transition of thought into action is effectively enabled. [Ghoshal and Barlett (1995)]
the Argument

It had been held by social-psychologists that the impact of the founder on the culture of the organization set the theme for future progress. To choose a direction, a leader must first have developed a mental image of a possible and desirable future state of the organization. This image, which we call a vision, may be as vague as a dream or as precise as a goal or mission statement. [Edgar Schein (1983)] .The critical point is that a vision articulates a view of a realistic, credible, attractive future for the organization, a condition that is better in some important ways than what now exists. [Stein and Pinchot (1998)] This idea of the *Meta Strategic Cycle* was related to both the values and the ends or purpose of the organization. [Limerick and Cunnington (1993)]

The above authors had attempted to represent processes such as these in their model of a "Metastrategic Cycle", a concept that links together vision, identity, configuration and organizational action. The Metastrategic cycle has four basic elements or stages within it: (i) Founding vision, (ii) Identity, (c) Configuration Design and (d) Systems of Action. This idea has been further elaborated

through the twin forces of ethics and governance. And to high excellence and sustainability were added on. [Sadri and Ajgaonkar (2002), Sadri and Jayashree (2011) Sadri and Makkar (2012)]

According to the above quoted authors the vision of the founder becomes established as a shared overall image, in the minds of those at the strategic apex of the organization, of the identity of the organization. This identity image consists of a number of elements, including: (a) its overarching values; and (b) a continuing vision of the potential of the organization as it moves through the environment and through time, that is a continuing vision of its mission. Identity has no reality outside the meanings attributed to the organization and shared by its members. It is, in effect, a socially constructed "reality". It is a holistic, inarticulate image, which often defies logic, represented subtly in the symbols, language, myth, labels, allegories and metaphors of the organization. But, for all its vagueness, it gives legitimacy and continuity to action.

The identity of an organization, then, is a holistic image, often vague and implicit, of the continuing nature of the organization as it moves through social space and time. Those at the strategic apex of the organization who hold this image must translate it into something more practical, into an integrated, operational model – a design which brings together a desired strategy, structure and culture of the organization into a coherent whole.

Bajaj” a brand of immense global proportions for scooters, had to *per force* switch to motorcycles in keeping with the customers’ preferences. With this switch they decided to discard “our faithful: hamara bajaj” imagery conjured by the old fashioned “B” word-mark. They shifted to a more angular, niftier, mobile “B” to appeal to the new customers. New factories and facilities; accent on product development, featured; shorter product life cycles and a dynamic marketing effort is very evident today. Radical change was necessary since tweaking would not do.

The configuration design of an organization provides a template for the development of the ongoing systems of action, which together form the organization. The entire metastrategic design, which links together configuration and identity, can become actuality only when various practical systems are developed to meet the needs of different product-market segments specified in the design. People come together to create these systems of action. They negotiate them, and give them substance. Any single individual may move between many such systems, particularly in network organizations. While people create these systems of action they may eventually come to have a momentum of their own. They become routine, and over time these routines may be slowly modified and changed.

Change can be visualised as consisting of long periods of stable structure (equilibrium), punctuated by short periods of intense change and reconfiguration when a radical idea and innovation happens. But that idea of radical change must be sold to the stakeholders who must unequivocally accept it. If not it would be detrimental to progress. [Gould (1989)]

B. *Case in Point*

In an otherwise stable university in Himachal Pradesh that had a solid academic brand since 2002 (supposedly) radical change post April 2012 brought with it a culture of subservience and instability just because the idea of change was neither realistic nor acceptable. Opening a small room, for instance, calling it an “Idea Factory” and placing student projects therein was a half-cocked attempt to usher in creativity and innovation even when an insecure non-academic top management by its actions and work culture as well as by its other attributes did not permit it. Similarly forming teams under the supervision of the Vice Chancellor like “academic Planning” “academic implementation” and “academic governance”, with the sole intention of making insecure faculty snitch on others was to say the least a bad idea. The upshot of it was the academics left and the mediocrity stayed on. Brand name plummeted and a once sought after institution began to be shunned even by local students who wanted admission.

The deep structure of things tends to persist until apparently events like a new technology act to trigger a complete restructuring of the system. In the case of IIMs and XLRI the strong academic and research culture withstood dramatic changes in 1990-1999 with the introduction of technology. Computer labs were kept open 24x7 with free internet access. This was a stark comparison to private institutes that had no internet lab except on paper and something similar that was operated on the eve of inspection by regulatory bodies only., Chaos was then progressive as this disequilibrium was dynamic and constructive. This is essentially what chaos theory is attempting to capture -order emerges through fluctuation and chaos [Gould, (1989), Tennenbaum, (1998)]. Others took a somewhat similar view in their paper when they said that one must collaborate with competitors to win. [Hamel, Doz and Prahalad (1989)]. Scholars in Japan spoke of bringing order out of chaos. [Ikujiro Nonaka (1988)] and this concept was later expanded in the famous address on the *four modes of knowledge conversion*, [Ikujiro Nonaka (1997)] On the other hand US further expand on the dynamics of this process when they say that in a system condition, an element fluctuates. It acts on the neighbouring elements one after another or competes with them, and the fluctuation begins to be amplified. It is the task of the leadership to give a symbiotic form that brings about the transition from competition to cooperation. [Senge (1990)] When a macroscopic pattern begins to emerge from such a dynamic co-operative phenomenon, a feedback to each element takes place, reinforcing the dynamic co-operation. Thus a definite order is fixed spontaneously and a definite function is performed forming a stable order. When the order becomes fixed, the organic system again carries on a similar process irreversibly. As the order of a system "becomes fixed", it is possible to discern a level of deep structure, a "dialectic" emerges.

The implications for organizations are profound. The model argues for processes that allow elements to engage in collaborative self-organization out of chaos. The elements must be free to import energy, to fluctuate. For an organization to renew itself, it must keep itself in a non-equilibrium state at all times. [Kanter (1989)]. Non-equilibrium does not imply catastrophe, and in fact it is the anti-thesis of inertial and portrays dynamism.

C. Case in Point:

Tata" a visibly global brand now, has transformed itself from the *benevolent giant* at the turn of the century to a *fighting machine*. In successive steps, starting with the dismantling of satrap- dominated internecine-warfare centric work culture in a sheltered business environment, without a uniform brand image to a professionally managed think-big focused line-of-business oriented, uniformly branded, synergistic global force. The GEO, the thinking arm of Tatas is comprised of a new breed of professionals from the industry - not the Tata stables. They have moved Tatas from a dominant local player to the international forum, concurrently building on the *leadership with trust* value promised to its stake holders. Thus Tata today is different company – nimble, risk taking and exciting, under a *different leader and a leadership team*. While the visible process is derived from the Malcolm Baldrige criteria, the magnitude of personal involvement and "giving substance" requires a reader's imagination given the size of the Tata organisation. While the current equilibrium is necessary, it is not sufficient to ensure Tatas' global sustainability.

Yet at the same time elements within the organization must be able to recognize and manage levels of deep structure, and transcend and change these into new structures, which are more consonant with chaotic changes in the environment. This, in effect, is what Shell found among long-surviving organizations. [de Geus (1988)] . It had been reported that they had one thing in common - a tolerance for experimentation and differences among their elements. They had highly autonomous units, which were permitted to move into new businesses and new industries. Our study of SMEs in India revealed that they owners often allowed their own processes to be chaotic enough to match the chaotic nature of the environment. With insecure top management chaos became the corporate watchword in many pharmaceutical units in both Punjab and in Jammu. But this chaos was directionless. Financial gloom and doom was inevitable.

In sum, continuous learning and experimentation allows reconfiguration and enhances creativity [Cummings and Oldham (1997)]. Those organizations which learn and adapt fastest are those which empower their elements to experiment. But they also have to act and think at a system-design level: they have to think about their co-operative identity, and move past it to a new identity and new configuration during periods of punctuation. Institutions of higher learning in India like the IIMs, XLRI, MDI and XIMB exemplify this facet beautifully.

Often it is not sufficient to characterize these systems as open, adaptive, non- equilibrium, or learning systems; they are all that and more; they are self-transcendent, which means that they are capable of representing themselves and therefore also of transforming themselves. They have to be able continuously to challenge and transform their own concepts of identity. This can be an extremely subtle process. [Walter Powell (1998)] As some others argue *self transcendence* means the capability to change one's own point of view, and therefore the capability to view a situation in a new light. [Pankow (1976)]. Alternatively one might say the ability to jump over one's shadow. The argument is in two parts: (a) To be truly self-transcendent, the organization must be able to overcome what Argyris call its own "defensive routines" which enable managers and others to stay within the relative comfort zone of the current deep structure, whatever is happening in the environment. (b) The organization must involve every member of the organization in the process, which moves from incremental to transformational change. Bass, for example, observes that when the firm is faced with a turbulent marketplace; when its products are born, live and die within the span of a few years; and/or when its current technology can become obsolete before it is fully depreciated; then transformational leadership needs to be fostered at all levels in the firm. More recently Sadri (2013) has similarly argued that all the different loci of brand management need to be credible, relevant, differentiating, value based and in line with corporate vision without sacrificing both creativity and innovation if the brand has to be sustainable.

During periods of apparent stability, too, widespread involvement is also required in both continuous improvement processes and in experimenting with new ideas. From these may emerge a new configuration? In sum, the innovative organization needs to be able to engage in changing and developing the entire metastrategic cycle, from change in organizational identity to constant change, experimentation and improvement in systems of action. It must thrive in conditions of both stability and discontinuity. It must recognize that these two states are essentially part of the same process. The processes required for continuous improvement are also those which enable transformation and self-redefinition.

D. Case in Point:

"Kaizen" at the manifest level is small-step improvements by improvement groups at the lowest level of organisation. It embraces large numbers and makes for an environment of (continuous) improvement. What is not so obvious, but a not welcome conditioning exercise, is that of priming the organisation for adopting "change", making a "change ready mindset. A moribund lamp making unit, near Pune, for instance, was beset with resistance to any change. As a wag put it "the cane in the chairs has changed more often than the incumbents"! 'Change', at regular intervals was at the Plant Manager level - with itinerant expatriates doing their 'punishment postings', till an Indian Manager took over. He introduced 'small group activity' in the lamp factory - and amidst great hilarity. And, the pilot team produced startling results - a ten fold reduction level in rejections of the most expensive lamp! The Group was recognised with the top award at the Company's Inter-Unit celebrations (quality). "Kaizen" had come to stay.' In three years more than 70% of people were involved in continuous improvement - but importantly, major breakthroughs were instituted: outsourcing, contract-manufacturing, extension of working hours by 12% (without overtime) to face competition.

The Innovation Paradigm

In theory learning that is encouraged from the top downwards implies both self-development and organizational development [Levinson and Rosenthal (1984)] and it proceeds particularly by questioning

taken for granted assumptions [Hurley and Hult (1998)]. Innovation contributes to continuous improvement and transformational change because it involves collaborative questioning by organizational members of their own actions. Its immediate focus of attention might be systems of action, meta-strategic design and/or organizational identity - but, even when focusing on the more apparently superficial level of systems of action, it remains alert to identity assumptions [Sennett (2006)]. This point in the Indian context was forcefully made in the Indian context when the author had argued that strategic focus in respect of quality, relevance and performance was possible only through merit review, human capital management, technology enabled business processes and performance assessment that was inherently creative and innovative. [Jayashree (2013)].

The essence of an innovative organization lies in a widely distributed capacity to question and redefine both individual and organizational identity. It is this unique autonomy of individuals that is the fundamental hallmark of an innovative enterprise. Underlying this distributed questioning capacity in an innovative organization is a set of fundamental shared beliefs and values that Revans explains above.

V. The Innovation Characteristics

The innovative organization contributes to continuous improvement and transformational change through a range of interdependent systems of action focused on individual and organizational development. Such an organization has the following characteristics: (a) A bias for reflection-in-action (b) Formation of learning alliances. (c) Development of external networks. (d) Multiple reward systems. (e) Creation of meaningful information. (f) Individual empowerment. (g) Leadership and vision. (h) Enhancement of the quality of mindsets. Earlier research threw up these eight features in great detail through out their argument. Roles and relations exist as a multidimensional web rather than a lateral flow: People work together across divisional, functional, and hierarchy boundaries easily. Senior managers are actively involved with creating and maintaining the processes and procedures necessary to support innovation (i.e., developing and diffusing decision-making tools, benchmarking, pushing for key changes like eliminating complexity). Innovation must be the strategy, and the whole organization has to accordingly support innovation as Nemeth has argued. The business definition is more broadly determined from a market orientation (e.g., transportation vs. railroads; information management vs. computers). [Sadri and Guha (2007)] . We now opine that the following features (at least in the Indian context) are important in making this multidimensional web possible.

A. *Organizing*

People need to focus directly on whole businesses so everyone in a business unit understands specific business domains, customers, and trends. Even if divisional or functional demarcations exist, thinking should be in comprehensible wholes vs. parts or individual steps. Thus breaking up the organization and organizing in the form of bite-sized wholes or entrepreneurial is important in evolving to this type.

B. *Evaluation*

A clear corporate strategy to innovation, such as measuring businesses on how much income comes from innovation (i.e., products at different stages of their life cycles) is important. Instead of an emphasis on reporting on what money has been spent and justifying expenses, a futures orientation is important since results from innovation are unpredictable in terms of the time taken investment and even the possibility of success. Thus the innovative organization's control system is strategic rather than operational.

C. *Commitment*

Since the focus is on innovation throughout the organization, there is no question of its importance. People develop participation on teams based on personal relationships, which is possible because the organizing system eliminates the need to negotiate roles and boundaries for every activity. Innovation activities are in fact focused, and so innovation is inherently doable, as opposed to being a problem. Innovation is part and parcel of peoples' daily experience and not an adjunct activity.

D. *Structure of the Organization*

The roles of the various levels of management have to be altered to support innovation. Instead of the traditional, hierarchy and functionally driven organization, an individualized organization comes into being. The traditional organization view sees management's role as ensuring that employee's ambitions concur with the organization's goals, it introduces checks and corrective actions, which we know as management controls. With the basic function of assuring compliance of work activity with the set goals, management controls are built into all stages of the firm's processes. Further, as an organization grows, management enhances and adds controls in an attempt to increase its sense of understanding of the organization. This is how eventually every aspect of the organization comes under control.

However, the emphasis on compliance takes priority over creativity and innovation. It results in an environment that impedes change, becomes antagonistic to productivity, and become a ubiquitous obstacle to excellence. A large part of the organizational effort is allocated to taking care of the mundane- i.e. the organization continues to transact its business in the usual way and operates in control of all sub-functions. Performance criteria are set based on how well one works within constraints of the control. There is little emphasis on how efficiently or effectively the organization is executing its underlined function and, more than anything else, how well it is working to enhance these functions for the future.

Corporate organizational theory accepts that control is a management function, but for the greater good of encouraging innovation in contemporary organizations, it needs to be evaluated very carefully. Top management wanted to give responsibility but would not part with authority. Top management wanted power without accountability. The former gave rise to despotic CEOs who led their companies into the gutter whereas the latter gave rise to a string of CEOs who wanted to be surrounded by sycophants and independently got rich as the organisations became poor. This was the Indian experience between 2010 and 2013 both in the worlds of industry and business as well as in the worlds of academics and research. As any scholar will vouchsafe, there is an indubitable link between MIS and MCS. Without MIS one just cannot incorporate MCS and without MCS we reduce MIS to a meaningless exercise very much like librarian in Umberto Eco's novel, *The Name of Rose*. Moreover the central function of all MCS is to retrieve information by way of effective feedback so as to improve on deliverables and control the means of production. This old model of constraint, control, compliance, and contract has to be replaced. And now the main job of top management was to create a context that changes behaviour. In fact, as information, knowledge, and expertise replace capital as the critical resource to be managed, top management's primary job is not defining the strategic content, it is framing the organizational context. And it meant replacing this compliance with self-discipline. Compliance by top management and their epigones was often converted to imply "subservience" and self-discipline was used to mean "obey orders". We wonder how these top level managers expected innovation and creativity to thrive! It was clear that they neither said what they meant not meant what they said at open house meetings.

E. *Case in point:*

Innovation takes root via 'internalisation'. On the shop floor when written instructions are no longer required we say that process/procedure is internalised. The issue is 'what' has been encrypted has to be replaced. The greater the degree of difference – the harder it is to rewrite. Innovative methods for re-encryption are also required. Conviction via (self) discovery is the way. In a SME organisation in Greater Mumbai, for instance, workers were indoctrinated that 'quality' of the factory's products were the best in India. That was a rallying point and a source of pride. "Quality" was defined in the manuals (prepared for the ISO certification) and product fault attributes were coded 'A, B & C' in line with the usual (decreasing) damage impact classification. This hoary wisdom had passed on with the 'technology transfer' from the JV partners. In the early 90's, the new manager, seeking to impress on the work force an urgent need to change for increased competitiveness, found himself 'stuck'. The issue: how to replace the older (frozen) mindset and bring home the paradigm shift. Innovation: a short circuit! He sent out batches of workers, with salesmen, to the dealer outlets and witness for themselves 'the buying criteria' of

an average consumer. Most teams came back sobered and chastened. 'C' faults (minor) were 'A' faults (major) in the eyes of the customers e.g. a scratch on the paintwork

Top management's critical role was as strategic architect, the creator of the structures and systems that controlled the company. But today the critical role is to become the builder of an institution. Operational matters are left to the second line of command leaving those at the top to do what they are supposed to: envision, think through, plan, strategise and actualise. More specifically they should be involved in (a) creating a culture of innovation, (b) encourage risk taking, (c) pooling resources since the need to optimise has been replaced by the need to maximise, (d) unofficial activity to meet legitimate corporate goals (f) sharing knowledge freely, (g) teamwork and project orientation, (h) divergent competencies (i) strong core values and (j) developing co-workers.

This means that Strategic initiatives must be well thought out preceded by scientific diagnosis and followed by objective revaluation. [Prakash, Dange and Jayashree (2007)]. Strategic initiatives to our mind thus have to:

- (i) Nurture and support the creative potential of employees with generally creative personalities and with innovative problem-solving styles, managers should ensure that these employees' interactions with their co-workers do not inhibit their ability to integrate divergent information, to pursue frame-breaking ideas, or to focus on their work.
- (ii) Realise that some co-worker interaction may actually provide important further motivation to these employees, by stimulating wider interests, adding complexity, or introducing some competitive pressure to enhance the novelty, usefulness, or number of their contributions relative to their co-workers. Thus, employees' high creative potential will be maximized when this potential is stimulated and motivated by the work context. Only when individuals with creative personalities and innovative problem-solving styles are excited by their work and free of external constraints" can they make full "use" of their divergent interests, tolerance of ambiguity, attention to complexity, self-confidence, and frame-breaking approaches.

vi. Conclusion

We all realise that India's economy is at crossroads. However, the promises of yester-years will remain promises if we keep doing more of the same. *Inventive adaptations* will have to take primacy of place. In our haste to achieve the goals enshrined in the '2050 Vision' there is every possibility that we will "copy" our way to failure. Western managerial philosophy is based on paucity of manpower: this cannot be an Indian premise. An Indian managerial model has to emerge: Japan did so fifty years ago and both India and China are doing now.

Our continuing research shows that the aforementioned thinking is insufficiently recognised for translation to action. Perhaps the final word should be given to the fact that the most precious asset of any organization is the one most readily overlooked i.e. its capacity to build on lived experience, to learn from its challenges and to turn-in a better performance by inviting all and sundry to work out for themselves what that performance might be. [Revans (1981)] Humankind is a product of *evolution* wherein the process as defined above has rolled out. Changes, today, on the other hand, are *revolutionary*. We need to define and invent systems which allow a good marriage – at least a convenient fit. We must find a solution to "future shock". To end this paper the author selects a quote from Kahlil Gibran: *to understand the heart and mind of a person, look not at what he has already achieved, but at what he aspires to*. The Indian experience squarely points towards the fact that creativity and innovation must be willed, planned and then executed. Understanding the human mind is the key issue and many a CEO has made the blunder of reading it wrongly. And it is here that the challenge of achieving innovation truly lies.

To be successful the CEO must lead by example and understand that business ethics and good governance hold the key to excellence and that excellence is achieved through consistent practice.

Excellence is a pie in the sky unless it converts into business sustainability. To do so it needs a corporate culture devoid of hypocrisy seeped in values that are robust and ethics that are vibrant. Unless the CEO is able to walk his talk and bring about a culture that sustains excellence, developmental growth will remain a pie in the sky and innovation will remain just an empty word in the business manager's lexicon. As Carl Jung would have said *we cannot change anything until we accept it*. And, acceptance of the organizational reality needs an honest heart and a clear mind that successful CEOs have and many others do not – therein lies perhaps the difference between chalk and cheese.

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